

Impossible Fibers Turbidity Meter Lab Equipment Guide

VEVOR Turbidity Meter
Model: TN1000

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- This instrument uses infrared light emitting diode (LED $860\pm 30\text{nm}$) as the light source and 90° scattering method, which is compliant with ISO 7027 and DIN EN 27027 standards for the determination of turbidity of solutions.
 - NTU stands for Nephelometric Turbidity Units. It represents a measurement of light scattered at a 90-degree angle to the incident light source, typically using a nephelometer. The higher the NTU value, the more suspended solids are present in the solution.
 - The instrument adopts 4 pieces of AA alkaline battery. Make sure there is no mixture of new&old batteries or different models of batteries.
1. Place the turbidity meter on a flat and level surface (Figure 1). Do not hold the instrument in your hand while operating.

Figure 1. Turbidity meter

2. Power on the instrument and long press the MEAS/ENTER button to start continuous measurement (do not insert the vial). Wait for 3-5 minutes.
3. Open the flip cover and place the 0.0 NTU calibration vial. Align the arrow on the vial lid with the arrow on the sample vial holder (Figure 2). Close the flip cover.

Figure.2 Calibration vial in the vial holder

4. Press the CAL/ESC button to enter the calibration menu, the cursor is 0 NTU. Press MEAS/ENTER to start calibration.
5. After calibration is done, press MEAS/ENTER to confirm. The check mark (✓) indicates that 0 NTU has been calibrated. (Figure 3).

Figure 3. 0 NTU calibration confirmation

6. Repeat the calibration with 20 NTU vial. For low turbidity measurements (measurements less than 2 NTU) test the 0 and 20 NTU before the test; then use 1# or 2# sample vial for measurement.
7. For high turbidity measurements, run 100 NTU, 400 NTU and 800 NTU before the tests. It is recommended to calibrate the equipment once a week, and test a calibration solution close to the sample solution.
8. If the calibration point has a large error, enter the calibration mode and repeat the calibration. The calibration point accuracy standards are as follows:

Calibration point	Accuracy for reference
0 NTU	≤ 0.05 NTU
20 NTU	$\leq \pm 0.2$ NTU
100 NTU	$\leq \pm 2$ NTU
400 NTU and 800 NTU	$\leq \pm 5$ NTU

9. Once the calibration is complete, press the CAL/ESC button to exit the calibration menu.
10. Collect the sample solution with a clean container and add 18 mL of the solution to the vial and close the lid.
11. Slowly flip the sample vial a few times and let it stand for 2-5 minutes to eliminate potential air bubbles.
12. Clean off the surface of the vial to ensure it is dry, clean and free of stains. Apply a small drop of silicone oil on the surface of the vial and wipe it off with the micro-fiber cloth. Wipe again with filter paper. Grip the vials from the cap and bottom to avoid any fingerprints on the surface of the vial. It is not necessary to use silicone oil for each calibration and measurement . Apply silicone oil once a week. In between just clean the surface with filter paper.
13. Open the flip cover and place the sample vial. Wait for 2 minutes to eliminate inaccurate measurements since the solution will experience some shaking when the vial moves.
14. Press MEAS/ENTER, the screen will display the progress bar and the measured value will be displayed in 10 seconds.
15. Record the measurement. To take the next measurement , press MEAS/ENTER again.
16. Once all samples have been measured, ensure the sample vials are cleaned thoroughly, ensuring they are free from smudges and scratches. Keep all the calibration solutions and measurement vials in the carrying case ready for the next user.
17. Turn off the power.